

MAGNETO-CHEMICAL STUDIES IN VALENCY. PART IV. TETRAPOSITIVE NICKEL AS ALKALI NICKEL PERIODATES

BY PRIYADARANJAN RÂY AND BYOMKES SARMA

Preparation and properties of sodium and potassium nickel periodates, containing tetrapositive nickel, have been described. The compounds are represented by the formula, $\text{Na}(\text{K})\text{NiIO}_6, x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, apparently a mixed or double salt of ortho-periodic acid of which the hydrogen atoms are replaced by one alkali metal and one quadrivalent nickel atom. The determination of magnetic susceptibility, giving a very low moment value ($\mu_B = 1.1$), indicates, however, that the compounds belong to the class of penetration complexes having octahedral configuration of oxygen atoms around nickel with d^2sp^3 hybrid bonds. It is, therefore, assumed that $[\text{Ni}(\text{IO}_6)]$ is present as a univalent complex anion in their molecule. The diamagnetic character of alkali silver and alkali copper periodates containing tripositive silver and copper, as observed by Malatesta, has also been accounted for in a similar manner.

It has been reported by some previous workers that manganese, cobalt, copper and silver in their trivalent state can form double or complex periodates with periodates of alkali or other metals (cf. Berg, *Compt. rend.*, 1899, 128, 673; Price, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1903, 30, 182; Urtis, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1925, 44, 423; Malaprade, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1935, v, 2, 359; 1936, v, 3, 361; 1938, 5, 582; *Compt. rend.*, 1937, 204, 979; Malatesta, *Gazzetta*, 1941, 71, 467, 580). Malatesta also measured the magnetic susceptibility of those periodates containing copper and silver in the trivalent state, and found them all to be diamagnetic. The manifestation of higher valencies by copper and silver in combination with periodates suggested that the element nickel might as well behave in a similar manner, particularly in view of the fact that this element was already known to exhibit a higher valency in the form of a black oxide and in the so-called niccolites. Furthermore, the preparation of a quadrivalent nickel molybdate in combination with alkali or alkaline earth molybdate by Hall (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 692) supported this idea. These latter substances form fine purple-black crystalline compounds and, as has been shown in Part III of this series (Rây, Bhaduri and Sarma, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 51) from a consideration of their magnetic properties, should be regarded as salts of complex heteropolymolybdic acid with tetrapositive nickel as the central atom. Guided by this analogy, we succeeded in preparing specimens of sodium and potassium nickel periodates with nickel atom in the tetrapositive state. The preparation and properties of these substances are described below.

It might, however, be mentioned here that Malaprade (*Compt. rend.*, 1937, 204, 979) also tried to prepare a nickel periodate with nickel in a higher valency state, but failed to obtain any positive result.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium Nickel Periodate.— $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 g.) dissolved in water was treated with a solution of sodium periodate, $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6$ (5 g.). The mixture was heated nearly to

boiling and then oxidised by the addition of sodium persulphate (8 g.), added in small quantities at a time. The light green solution gradually turned darker in colour with separation of fine, dark purple, almost black crystals with shining metallic lustre. The crystals show a great tendency to adhere to the walls of the beaker in the form of a bright mirror, and are practically insoluble in cold water. They were washed first with dilute sodium persulphate solution and then with hot water. The crystals were dried in air. The substance emits an odour of ozonized oxygen in air and readily decomposes when heated. [Found : Ni, 18.20 ; Na, 6.99 ; I, 38.86, 40.20 ; O (total active), 24.35, O(Ni⁴⁺), 4.57, 4.78 ; H₂O (by difference), 5.5. NaNiO₆.11.2O requires Ni, 18.19 ; Na, 7.13 ; I 39.36, O (total active) 24.79 ; O(Ni⁴⁺), 4.96 ; H₂O, 5.6 per cent.]

Nickel was estimated as nickel dimethylglyoxime after decomposition of the substance with SO₂ and HCl. Sodium was estimated as sodium sulphate in the filtrate from nickel. Iodine was estimated as silver iodide after decomposition and reduction of the substance with SO₂ and dilute sulphuric acid. The total active oxygen was determined from the amount of iodine liberated by the substance from an acid solution of potassium iodide. After making due allowance for the periodate radical, as determined from the amount of silver iodide, the valency of nickel was deduced from its oxygen equivalent.

Potassium nickel periodate was prepared like the corresponding sodium compound, using potassium periodate, KIO₄, and potassium persulphate in place of the sodium salts. It resembles its sodium analogue in properties. [Found : Ni, 17.78, 17.83 ; K, 12.16 ; I, 39.04, 38.6 ; O (total active), 23.77 ; O(Ni⁴⁺), 4.28 ; H₂O (by difference), 2.64. KNiO₆.0.5H₂O requires Ni, 17.78 ; K, 11.84 ; I, 38.48 ; O (total active), 24.24 ; O(Ni⁴⁺), 4.85 ; H₂O, 2.73 per cent].

Malaprade (*loc. cit.*) oxidised nickel hydroxide, suspended in a mixture of potassium periodate and caustic potash solution, with potassium persulphate. A brown solution was obtained, from which, however, no compound could be isolated.

Measurements of Magnetic Susceptibility.—Measurements were made in a Gouy's balance with a field strength of 10.16×10^3 gauss.

Substance.	<i>t.</i>	$\chi_g \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M^{\text{cor}} \times 10^6$.	μ_B .
NaNiO ₆ .H ₂ O	31°	1.284	415	510	1.11
KNiO ₆ .0.5H ₂ O	"	1.143	376	473.3	1.08

The diamagnetic correction for [IO₄]³⁻ was deduced from the measurement of susceptibility value of Na₃H₂IO₆ for which $\chi_g = -0.2933 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\chi_M = -86.22 \times 10^{-6}$. From this χ_M for [IO₄]³⁻ = -65.8×10^{-6} .

DISCUSSION

The magnetic moment values for the sodium and potassium periodates, described above, show that the tetrapositive nickel atom in these compounds cannot contain any unpaired electron. For, the observed moment value is less than even $1.73 \mu_B$, required for the presence of a single unbalanced electron on the basis of Bose-Stoner's formula. This

seems to suggest that the substances in the pure state would possibly be diamagnetic, the observed paramagnetic susceptibility of low moment value arising presumably from partial dissociation due to their temperature instability. The composition of these compounds, $\text{Na(K)NiIO}_6 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, corresponds apparently to a mixed salt of ortho-periodic acid, H_5IO_6 , the hydrogen atoms of which are replaced by one quadrivalent nickel and one alkali metal atom. But a quadrivalent nickel ion in the normal state should give a moment value of 4.9 Bohr due to four unpaired electrons, while the observed value indicates the absence of even a single unpaired electron. The diamagnetic character of alkali and alkaline-earth nickel molybdates with nickel in the quadrivalent state has been accounted for in part III (*loc. cit.*) as due to the formation by the nickel atom of a heteropoly-acid complex of the penetration type with d^2sp^3 hybrid octahedral bonds. In this it resembles the tripositive cobalt in all cobaltic complexes. The fact that the tetrapositive nickel and tripositive cobalt possess the same number of electrons justifies this assumption. In the present case of alkali nickel periodates, however, their very simple composition precludes any such attempt at representing them as heteropoly-acid complex of the above type. Nevertheless, their magnetic property demands that they should also be represented as a penetration complex with the tetrapositive nickel atom constituting the centre of a co-ordination octahedron with d^2sp^3 hybrid bonds. A quadrivalent nickel atom like those of its higher homologues, quadrivalent palladium and platinum, is likely to have a co-ordination number of six, resembling trivalent cobalt with which it is iso-electronic. This should make the complex diamagnetic. The very low moment value, as actually observed, is possibly due to a partial dissociation of these substances into Na(K)IO_4 and NiO_2 , as suggested above.

The possible structure of these alkali nickel periodates in the crystalline state may, therefore, be represented as follows. Each nickel, iodine or potassium atom is surrounded octahedrally by six oxygen atoms; and each oxygen is bound to one nickel, one iodine and one potassium atom, showing a co-ordination number of three. Every oxygen atom constitutes a common corner for all the three octahedra which possibly share edges with each other. The bonds between oxygen and nickel, as well as those between oxygen and iodine, are predominantly covalent, due to strong polarizing power of the highly positive nickel (quadrivalent) and iodine (heptavalent) atoms, while those between potassium and oxygen atoms are purely ionic. The compounds should, therefore, be represented by the formula, $\text{Na(K)[Ni}^{\text{IV}}(\text{IO}_6)]$.

A similar explanation can also be advanced in order to account for the diamagnetic character, as observed by Malatesta (*loc. cit.*), of the alkali-silver and alkali-copper periodates containing tripositive silver and copper atoms (*vide supra*). The composition of these compounds are represented by the formulae, $\text{M}_7\text{Cu}(\text{IO}_6)_2$ and $\text{M}_7\text{Ag}(\text{IO}_6)_2$, where M_7 may be Na_7 , K_7 , K_6H , Na_6H , or KHNa_6 . In these, the trivalent Ag or Cu atom is quadri-coordinated with oxygen in a planar square configuration forming dsp^2 hybrid bonds. For, a trivalent copper, being iso-electronic with bivalent nickel, is likely to show a co-ordination number of four. Similarly, a tripositive silver atom is already known to be quadri-coordinated like bivalent palladium with which it is iso-electronic (*cf. Ráy and Chakravarty, J. Indian Chem. Soc., 1944, 21, 47*). Each iodine atom is

surrounded octahedrally as usual by six oxygen atoms. Two such iodine octahedra are bound by the central copper or silver atom through a pair of oxygen atoms of each octahedron, forming a square planar configuration around the metal atom. Alkali metal atoms occur in suitable co-ordination with oxygen atoms between these individual complex units of metal-periodate groups. Hydrogen atom may replace the alkali metal atom occasionally. Water molecules obviously enter the empty channels or holes in the crystal. As before, the bonds between silver (copper) and oxygen atoms, as well as those between iodine and oxygen atoms, are essentially covalent, while the alkali metal atoms form purely ionic bonds with oxygen atoms. The compounds should, therefore, be represented by the formula,

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

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